

NSF Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure

NSDF AHM @ SDSC
12-13 April 2023

Outline

- Background
- Architecture
- Implementation
- Demo / Usage Example
- Discussion

NSDF AAI - Motivation

- Restricted/secured services

- Vast data/resources

- Personalized services

- Different types users

Reference Architecture

- AARC Blueprint Architecture - <https://aarc-project.eu/architecture/>

Software building blocks to implement federated access management solutions for international research collaborations

Technology Used

- ✓ Low maintenance cost
- ✓ Highly adopted by the community
- ✓ AARC blueprint architecture
- ✓ Identity and access management solutions
- ✓ SSO Authentication
- ✓ External IdPs
- ✓ Admin and Account management consoles

Implementation – user resource request

Configuration - CILogon

OpenID Connect (OIDC)

CILogon provides a standards-compliant OpenID Connect (OAuth 2.0) interface to federated authentication for cyberinfrastructure (CI).

We recommend using a Certified OpenID Connect Implementation when connecting to CILogon. We plan to obtain OpenID Certification for CILogon's OIDC implementation in the future.

Client Registration

Authorized CILogon subscribers may use their COManage Registry profile to register and manage OIDC clients. Log into your Registry and then click "OIDC Clients".

Basic Authentication service tier (free) users should register your client at <https://cilogon.org/oauth2/register> and wait for notice of approval. Please register your callback URLs on that page with care. They are the only callback URLs that may be used by your client unless you later contact help@cilogon.org and request a change to your registration.

Kubernetes users: It is recommended that you specify a refresh token lifetime of 10 days (864000 seconds) or longer if your cluster requires authentication.

Client Configuration

OpenID Connect (OIDC)

CILogon's OpenID Connect (OIDC) endpoint:

- **Discovery:** <https://cilogon.org/well-known/openid-configuration>

① **OAuth 2.0**

Demo (User)

<https://idp.nationalsciencedatafabric.org/auth/realms/nsdf/account>

NSF NSDF CVDC

Powered by

English v

LOG IN

USERNAME or EMAIL

PASSWORD

Remember me [Forgot Password?](#)

SIGN IN

Or sign in with

CILogon

New user? [Register](#)

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Consent to Attribute Release

NSF National Science Data Fabric (NSDF) requests access to the following information. If you do not approve this request, do not proceed.

- Your CILogon user identifier
- Your name
- Your email address

Select an Identity Provider

Google

Remember this selection

Log On

By selecting "Log On", you agree to the [privacy policy](#).

For questions about this site, please see the FAQs or send email to help@cilogon.org.
Know your responsibilities for using the CILogon Service.
See acknowledgements of support for this site.

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English Sign Out

Account

- Account
- Password
- Authenticator
- Federated Identity
- Sessions
- Applications

Edit Account

* Required fields

USERNAME * irodero

EMAIL * irodero@gmail.com

FIRST NAME * ivan

LAST NAME * rodero

Cancel Save

Demo (Administration)

- User management, group management (authorization)
- Identity providers (e.g., CILogon)
- Clients (e.g., applications, services), etc.

The screenshot displays the Nsdf administration interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with the 'Nsdf' logo and a dropdown arrow. Below the logo, the sidebar is divided into two sections: 'Configure' and 'Manage'. The 'Configure' section includes links for Realm Settings, Clients, Client Scopes, Roles, Identity, Providers, User Federation, and Authentication. The 'Manage' section includes Groups (highlighted in red), Users, Sessions, Events, Import, and Export. The main content area is titled 'User Groups' and features a 'Groups' tab and a 'Default Groups' button. A search bar with a magnifying glass icon and a 'View all groups' button are present. Below the search bar is a table with a 'Groups' header and one row containing 'sample_resource'. To the right of the table are buttons for 'New', 'Edit', 'Cut', 'Paste', and 'Delete'.

AAI Integration Example in VDC

portal.datacollaboratory.org

- Account management (associated with AAI system)

The screenshot shows the user interface of the VDC portal. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the University of Utah logo and a home icon on the left, and menu items: DATA DISCOVERY, APPLICATIONS, SYSTEM STATUS, JOB MONITORING, WORKFLOWS, and ACCOUNT on the right. Below the navigation bar is a large banner image of a crowd of people in red shirts with the text "Welcome Ivan Rodero" overlaid in white. Underneath the banner is a table with account details:

Claim	Value
Username	irodero@gmail.com
Name	Ivan Rodero
Email	irodero@gmail.com
Valid token	✓

Below the table, the "GROUPS:" section lists "1: vdc_user". The "TOKEN:" section shows the token "wpkNKN0eEA" and the "LIFETIME: 6 DAY(S) 23 HRS 56 MIN 57 S". There are "REFRESH" and "COPY" buttons below the token. At the bottom of the account management area, there are "MANAGE ACCOUNT" and "LOGOUT" buttons.

The footer of the page contains the VDC logo, the NSDF logo, and social media icons for Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube. Text in the footer states: "Virtual Data Collaboratory is supported by its members institutions and the United States National Science Foundation through award numbers 1640834, 2220826."

Example – Python (user token and info)

```
import json

import requests

server_config = json.loads(open('config.json').read())

url = server_config['url']

client_id = server_config['client_id']

client_secret = server_config['client_secret']

headers = server_config['headers']

def user_info(name, password):

    payload = {"grant_type": "password",
              "client_id": client_id,
              "client_secret": client_secret}

    payload['password'] = password

    payload['username'] = name

    tokens = json.loads(requests.post(url, data=payload, headers=headers, verify=False).content)

    print(json.dumps(tokens, indent=2))

    payload = {"client_id": client_id,
              "client_secret": client_secret,
              "username": name,
              "token": tokens['access_token']}

    response = json.loads(requests.post(url+'/introspect', data=payload, headers=headers, verify=False).content)

    print(json.dumps(response, indent=2))

user_info('nsdf', 'test')
```

Example – Python (user token and info)

```
{
  "access_token": "eyJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IkpXZWQ9M4HoyKyJw",
  "expires_in": 300,
  "refresh_expires_in": 1800,
  "refresh_token": "eyJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IkpXZWQ9M4HoyKyJw",
  "token_type": "Bearer",
  "not-before-policy": 0,
  "session_state": "158a44fe-35ad-485a-83ef-34c196be4982",
  "scope": "email profile"
}
{
  "exp": 1681303299,
  "iat": 1681302999,
  "jti": "ed5ffecb-384f-47ae-a820-22b4a090b533",
  "iss": "https://idp.nationalsciencedatafabric.org/auth/realms/nsdf",
  "aud": "account",
  "sub": "23d5317e-6068-4290-bfb5-3a6b3501d7c0",
  "typ": "Bearer",
  "azp": "api",
  "session_state": "158a44fe-35ad-485a-83ef-34c196be4982",
  "name": "Fist name Last name",
  "given_name": "Fist name",
  "family_name": "Last name",
  "preferred_username": "nsdf",
  "email": "nsdf@example.com",
  "email_verified": false,
  "acr": "1",
  "realm_access": {
    "roles": [
      "offline_access",
      "default-roles-nsdf",
      "uma_authorization"
    ]
  },
  "resource_access": {
    "account": {
      "roles": [
        "manage-account",
        "manage-account-links",
        "view-profile"
      ]
    }
  },
  "scope": "email profile",
  "sid": "158a44fe-35ad-485a-83ef-34c196be4982",
  "client_id": "api",
  "username": "nsdf",
  "active": true
}
```

Example

Create a simple JavaScript code that uses keycloak to authenticate a user and retrieve their information:

Sure! Here's a simple example of how to use Keycloak in JavaScript to authenticate a user and retrieve their information:


```
javascript Copy code

// Initialize Keycloak instance
var keycloak = new Keycloak({
  url: 'http://localhost:8080/auth',
  realm: 'myrealm',
  clientId: 'myapp'
});

// Authenticate user
keycloak.init({ onLoad: 'login-required' }).success(function(authenticated)
  // If authenticated, retrieve user information
  if (authenticated) {
    console.log(keycloak.token); // Access token
    console.log(keycloak.refreshToken); // Refresh token
    console.log(keycloak.idToken); // ID token

    // Retrieve user profile
    keycloak.loadUserProfile().success(function(profile) {
      console.log(profile); // User profile object
    });
  }
}).error(function() {
  console.log('Authentication error');
});
```

Discussion

- Protect and access management (data portals, APIs, dashboards, etc.)
- Engagement with stakeholders
- Integration
 - NSDF components
 - Use cases
- Deployment model
 1. Centralized NSDF service
 2. **Federated authentication/authorization** (secure exchange of identity, authentication, and authorization information)
 3. Other models?

Thank you!

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